

THE PROBLEMS OF NO PHILOLOGY DIRECTION TEACHING ENGLISH WITH NEW METHODS

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Abstract. *Communicative Language Teaching method is widely used during the speaking and listening classes. Also, teach use new vocabulary words orally. In many cases they do mistakes while writing words of foreign origin and long words as well.*

Keywords: *approaches, methodological options, representatives, discussions, debates, classroom, communicative Language Teaching, reflects.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ НЕФИЛОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОБУЧЕНИЯ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ НОВЫМИ МЕТОДАМИ

Аннотация. *Коммуникативный метод обучения языку широко используется на уроках говорения и аудирования. Кроме того, учите использовать новые словарные слова в устной форме. Во многих случаях они допускают ошибки при написании слов иностранного происхождения, а также длинных слов.*

Ключевые слова: *подходы, методологические варианты, представители, дискуссии, дебаты, класс, коммуникативное обучение языку, рефлексия.*

The proliferation of approaches and methods is a prominent characteristic of contemporary second and foreign language teaching. To some, this reflects the strength of our profession. Invention of new classroom practices and approaches to designing language programs and materials reflects a commitment to finding more efficient and more effective ways of teaching languages. The classroom teacher and the program coordinator have a wider variety of methodological options to choose from than ever before. They can choose methods and materials according to the needs of learners, the preferences of teachers, and the constraints of the school or educational setting. To other, however, the wide variety of method options currently available confuses rather than comforts. Methods appear to be based on very different views of what language is and how a language is learned. Students will have to speak English everywhere in order to communicate: in the store, in supermarkets, in the street, in the classroom, in dining halls and in restaurants. Many foreign students attend ESL classes before getting academic courses. If we'll look at the numbers, students represent the majority of foreign students. There are more than three hundred students at the university every year. Since English classes for foreign students consist of 15-18 students, there are usually about students in each group. The same problem exists with students. The schedule of the classes is prepared beforehand, so that students can choose the suitable time and teacher for them. Students usually try to get in the same group with their friends. It creates one of the main problems. When there are more than three or four representatives of one nation in a group, those students usually speak native language with each other during the 256 English classes as well. Usually, students do less progress than the representatives of other countries. This is because they keep speaking in native, English language. It also influences their achievements during the classes. The problems which may occur with communicative language teaching in Uzbekistan is are as follows 1. less accurate grammar 2. mistakes of students may leave unchecked by teachers in some cases 3. relatively

more mistakes appear in writing (than in other methods) 4. less accurate pronunciation Let us bring examples to the statements brought above. As it is written above, in the form of social interaction activities of communicative language teaching are included debates, discussions, dialogues and role plays, skits and others which help to increase the social skills of the students. In this point of view teachers pay attention to the opinion of the student, what the student want to say. Usually teachers don't interrupt the student's speech to correct grammatical mistakes that they have done. Because if they do so they might create the thought in the student's mind that they should speak only in a case when they are sure not to make any grammatical mistake. Or sometimes students might easily get ashamed. Planning to tell it after the students` speech unintentionally teachers forget the fifty percent of the errors that they would like to tell. As well in Uzbekistan University in English classes for foreign students discussions and debates are used a lot in order to develop speaking skills of the foreign students. The same defects I have observed during intermediate level of the ESL classes there too. The students have to do class presentation about their own culture. It may be about proverbs, games, folktales, forms of address, standards of conduct, ceremonies, and holidays of their countries. The teacher never interrupts any student while talking. Neither have they corrected pronunciation mistakes, nor grammatical ones. As a result of which for some students it became more difficult to produce sentences accurately, to use the grammar correctly, to have the right pronunciation of the words. Teacher usually corrects mistakes after the students' speech. Let us bring another example on functional communication activities of the communicative language teaching method. It is speaking 4 (intermediate) class. The teacher has the students divide into groups of three. Since there are 15 students, there are five groups of three students. One member of each group is given a picture strip story. There are six pictures in a row on a piece of paper, but no words. The pictures tell a story. The student with the story shows the first picture to the other members of his group, while covering the remaining five pictures. The other students try to predict what they think will happen in the second picture. The first student tells them whether they are correct or not. He then shows them the second picture and asks them to predict what the third picture will look like. After the entire series of pictures has been shown, the group get a new strip story and they change the roles, giving the first student an opportunity to work with a partner in making predictions. As it is obvious from the examples, we can see that there is no any feedback or correction of mistakes from the side of the teacher. During the group work teacher observes the students, but he/she cannot observe everybody at the same time. That is why some mistakes remain uncorrected. Student remains unfamiliar about his mistake. Another point is that communicative language teaching method being specialized mostly in improving oral and communicative skills of the students, weakens the writing skills of the students. Communicative Language Teaching method is widely used during the speaking and listening classes. Students use new vocabulary words orally. In many cases they do mistakes while writing words of foreign origin and long words as well. Another new method that often used in English classes is Cooperative Language Teaching method which is also known as a collaborative language teaching. This method is one of the widely used in all classes of English as it includes all types of group works. The problems which may occur within this method are: a. passive students of the class remain passive b. Each member of the group prepares its own part and it results in not knowing the task as a whole. c. Attention is paid to that aspect of learning which is considered to be important by the student. d. In some cases, students are discouraged being graded for the work

of the whole group. e. students may shift to their native languages while discussing the problem or topic. f. passive participation is observed by the members of group in group works in informal cooperative learning group type of cooperative language learning. Teachers divide students into the groups paying attention to their learning potential. They try to mix the students with different levels, so that there will not be a group of only passive students or a group of only active students. Teachers make sure that there are students with different levels: passive, active and normal. Teacher divides fifteen students into three groups of five. Gives the theme to each group and asks them to make a presentation on their themes. Teacher gives the students thirty minutes. Active students in the group immediately begin discussing what they will do, until passive students just begin taking a pencil as if they are going to write some ideas. Passive students can't get involved into the group as much as the actives do. As a result of which two or three active students do the main part of group's work. Passive students remain to be passive. This situation happens a lot in informal group working. In order to avoid this problem teacher gives a certain task to the each student in the group. When the students are divided into the groups, works are divided into the parts. In the activities like corporative projects students identify subtopics for each group member. Each student gets his own part of work and has to deal up with that. The student makes some research, or prepares only his own part. But there appears another problem. It is that each member of the group prepares only his own part of the work, rest remains for other members to work on. It means that some aspects of the work remain unfamiliar to the members of the group. Students know properly only their part of work. For example, in reading 257 class. Reading for beginners teacher divides the students into small groups. There are four groups of four. Teacher gives the students different part of the story. Each group gets one part. Students read their parts, and work on the vocabulary. After ten minutes they make a new group. Two members of one group moves to the next group two remain at their places, and others join them. In each group students tell their part of story, new words from the part, and then listen to their part of story. Then the students change the group again and do the same thing. The third time, students come to their original group and tell the whole story from the beginning. As we can see from the activity described above, the story- text is learned from the aspect which is considered to be important by the members of the groups. New vocabulary words that one group choose may be not new for the other, or the opposite of it, the words which are looked at as not new by one group may be unfamiliar for the other. At the end the students have a worksheet to match the new words with its definition. Every student does the test on his own. Their scores depend on their results as a group. This rule sometimes may discourage the students who have done well. They may think that it is not fair to be punished for others fault who has done worse at the tests. It also changes the attitude of students who have done well towards the rest of the group. Let us take another example. As we have mentioned before if there are more than two students who are representatives of one nation and who share the same language other than English, they may easily shift to their native language not noticing it themselves. Teachers use jigsaw type of cooperative language learning in speaking classes. Instructor divides the class into three groups of five. Each member of the group gets different piece of information. Students regroup in topic groups and compose people of the same piece. They share information with each other. Then they go to their first groups. Each student produces an assignment or test from their own part of a group project. The problem here is that the students study properly only their part of work and other parts of it remain less familiar to them. As the result of which students don't learn the

whole theme properly. Another problem can occur in informal cooperative learning. She divides the group into two groups of eight. She gives the topic and groups take opposite positions. Panel of discussions gives the thirty percent of their total grade from the course. That is why teacher gives them three class time period in order to work with the group. Students come to the class and work with their group members on their own. In this method language objectives are dictated by the text. Here are the problems which happen within this method in the classroom: 1. New grammatical theme from the text is less understandable for the foreign students 2. Students pay much attention to the meaning of the text when they read it not to the grammar Foreign students usually are taught grammatical theme first then are given text to find the means of the exact grammar that is passed by the teacher. Teacher explains the grammatical theme properly. This is a usual procedure in home countries of foreign student.

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